

English Translation of
Schnecken im Brandungssand

by ADOLF SEILACHER

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Adolf Seilacher's report on his field observations of olivid gastropods and their behavior on sandy beaches of the Pacific coast of El Salvador is pertinent to recent research into the behavioral and community ecology of these and related species in the tropical East Pacific. So far the paper has not been widely accessible as it was published in German in the journal of the Senckenbergische Naturforschende Gesellschaft in Frankfurt am Main, of which no electronic version is available to date. This English translation is provided to increase the visibility of Seilacher's seminal work.

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Translator's Notes

Formatting, structure, and pagination of the translation follows the original closely. A statement on a certain page of the translation will be found on the same page in the original.

In the translated text, statements to which the following notes refer are marked ^{T1} through ^{T8}.

^{T1} The animal SEILACHER called *Olivella (Pachyoliva) columellaris* actually is *Olivella (Pachyoliva) semistriata* GRAY 1839; compare TROOST *et al.*, 2011, *Biota Neotropica* **12**, 101–113 (doi.org/10.1590/S1676-06032012000200011).

^{T2} Concerning wave dynamics on the beach, SEILACHER did not refer to swash (incoming turbulent wave) and backwash (smooth seaward flow) by unambiguous technical terms, but by descriptive expressions (such as "Aufstrom" and "Rückstrom", literally up-stream and back-stream). Rather than paraphrasing these terms in English, I used *swash* and *backwash* throughout for clarity.

^{T3} The term propodium refers to a morphologically distinct, anterior portion of the foot. In Olividae including *Olivella*, the propodium is crescent-shaped and separated from the main part of the foot (metapodium) by dorsal and ventral furrows. SEILACHER applied the term in an unusual way, as the "tentacle-like body appendages" he referred to are not propodia but lateral appendages of the propodium.

^{T4} Four Å equal 0.4 nm, not 4 nm as SEILACHER suggested.

^{T5} The phrase "Globulin-Moleküle des menschlichen Blutserums" (globulin molecules of the human blood serum) is ambiguous, as these globulins comprise a multitude of proteins that vary in molecular weight by an order of magnitude. Human serum albumins, common proteins that at under 70 kDa are smaller than all human globulins, have known hydrodynamic radii of 3.3–4.1 nm (JACHIMSKA *et al.*, 2008, *Langmuir* **24**, 6866–6872, doi.org/10.1021/la800548p) and would be retained by mucus nets of 0.4 as well as 4 nm mesh size.

^{T6} The taxonomy of the *Agaronia* spp. in the region remains unclear. The species studied by SEILACHER later was tentatively identified as *Agaronia propatula* CONRAD 1849 (ROBINSON & PETERS, 2018, *PeerJ* **6**, e4714, doi.org/10.7717/peerj.4714).

^{T7} OLSSON (1956, p. 164) described predation on *Olivella semistriata* (probably *Olivella (Pachyoliva) columellaris* SOWERBY 1825, see TROOST *et al.* cited under ^{T1}) by *Oliva undatella* and *Agaronia hiatula* at "Charapota between Manta and Bahia" (probably Charapotó, 00°15'S 80°29'W) in Ecuador, not in Peru.

^{T8} The inconsistent usage of em dashes (—) in the original reference list apparently caused confusion resulting in the deletion of one author's name (N. MACGINITIE). Em dashes are omitted and author's names are always given in full in the translated reference list.

Snails in the surf sand.

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With 10 Figures.

The harsh living conditions of exposed sandy beaches and the adaptations of animals living there were discussed a few years ago (SEILACHER 1953, p. 263) in this journal.

In that context, the pea-sized snail *Umbonium vestiarium* was mentioned. Although these snails often occur in large quantities on the beaches of India, they usually are hardly noticed because they are burrowed centimeter-deep in the sand — a fact, by the way, to which the unusual variability of color and patterning of the pretty shells of this species may be connected. Their coloration is not exposed and therefore is not as strongly subjected to selection as in free-living forms. From the uniform orientation of burrowed umbonia perpendicular to the beach, and from the

Figure 1–2. Two snails of the Salvadoran surf sand: 1) *Olivella columellaris*⁷¹ crawling on the surface. The crescent-shaped propodium is conspicuous even in this position due to its long lateral lobes and vivid markings. — 2) When in pursuit of the much smaller *Olivella*, *Agaronia* almost always remains below the sand surface. Therefore its propodium is little differentiated and as unpigmented as the entire foot, which here is spread out as an anchor during a “change of position”.

Figure 3

Figure 4

traces left on the surface, it was concluded at that time that they obtain their food from the backwash of the waves, in the manner of numerous surf animals. According to unpublished observations by Dr. KLAUS SANDER, *Umbonium* acquires its food together with its respiratory water from the sand surface by swirling. Thus, like bivalves with similar life-styles (e.g., *Donax*), the snail does not require strong surf and is found mainly on sheltered sections of the beaches.

On the Pacific coast of El Salvador (Central America), which I was able to study in 1954 as a guest of the Instituto Tropical de Investigaciones Cientificas¹, the snail *Olivella (Pachyoliva) columellaris*⁷¹ plays a similar role. Its shell resembles that of *Umbonium* in size and glossiness, but is more highly coiled. The structure of *Olivella*'s soft body and dental apparatus (radula) also indicate that it belongs to a different, less ancient order. Thus, similarities in construction and behavior of both forms certainly represent independently evolved convergences, and this is precisely what makes the comparison so interesting.

The life of *Olivella columellaris* is governed by the constant change of surf and tide. The crashing waves bring food but also the danger of being washed out. Therefore the snails remain hidden in the sand while a wave rises and during the first half of the backwash phase.⁷² Then, their tentacle-like body appendages, or propodia,⁷³ appear everywhere above the sand, standing transversely in the backwash. After less than a minute, they fold in toward the center (Figs. 6-8) and disappear into the sand again before the surface water has drained away completely. Only trident-shaped scour marks remain in the sand, bearing witness to the process (Fig. 3).

By its behavior, as it was already described in detail by O. SCHUSTER (1952), *Olivella columellaris* reminds one vividly of certain worms, e.g. *Scolecoplepis squamata* of the North Sea (cf. SEILACHER 1953) or the very similar *Nerine agilis* of the Salvadoran beach. These animals spread their two tentacles as glue rods in the back-

¹ I would also like to thank this institute and its director, Dr. A. PALACIOS, for their hospitality, Prof. Dr. A. MEYER-ABICH for his kind mediation, and last but not least the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft for their support.

Figure 3-4. Surface traces of *Olivella columellaris* at Los Blancos: 3) trident-shaped scour marks indicate snails hidden in the sand. One has crawled with hasty "looper" movements of foot and propodium to the upper right and burrowed in again. $\frac{1}{2} \times$. — 4) For unclear reasons all *Olivella* of a beach strip have emerged and crawled up to $\frac{1}{2}$ m beach-parallel to the left (i.e., not towards the water!). At the beginning of the crawl traces, trident-shaped scour marks often are visible still. At the end of the traces, a sharp turn and the location of re-burrowing are seen. $\frac{1}{13} \times$. — In both images the upper edge points landward.

Figure 5–8. The mucus net of *Olivella columellaris* inflates like a sail in the backwash. In its flow shadow the sand lies quietly, while narrow current threads in the center and on the sides (motion blur in Figure 5!) create the trident-shaped scour mark. When the net is retracted, the lobes of the propodium fold in while the net moves over the propodium's central part. In Figure 8, the gathered net is grasped by the white tip of the oral proboscis; the siphon appears below. (Images of different individuals; magnification 3–4 ×).

wash, and so it seemed obvious to think of a similar function in *Olivella*. In this case, however, what serves to collect food is not the tentacle-shaped propodium lobes but mucus nets that the snail expands on each side between the pro- and the metapodium. These nets are so delicate that they are easily overlooked in the turbulent surf, especially when they have just been deployed. Only towards the end of the catching act do they stand out a little more clearly, when captured plankton lays a faint brownish color on them. Finally, the nets are retracted (Fig. 10b-e) and eaten by the trunk-shaped mouth.

Mucus nets of this kind, although unknown so far in snails, are not a unique invention. Such devices are known, for example, from the bristle worm *Chaetopterus variopedatus* of the North American west coast (Fig. 9). Its tubular net is excreted continuously by body appendages that connect in an arc-like shape, and is retracted at the same velocity further back through special organs. In contrast, the net of another worm, the echiuroid *Urechis caupo* (Fig. 9), is eaten at regular intervals and replaced by a new one. Both worms live in U-shaped tubes through which they actively pump respiratory water, from which they filter fine food particles by the transversely expanded nets.

G. E. MACGINITIE, to whom we owe the detailed knowledge of these two worm species, also has used organic solutions to investigate the mesh size of their mucus

Figure 9: Mucus nets of worms (dotted) are expanded transversely in the U-shaped living tube. They filter the respiratory stream (arrows), which in *Chaetopterus* is produced by rudder stroke, in *Urechis* by peristalsis. (Redrawn after G. E. & N. MACGINITIE 1949, strongly reduced in size).

nets (1945). It is about 4 Å (= 4 millionths of a mm),⁷⁴ small enough to retain, for example, the globulin molecules of human blood serum.⁷⁵ This value applies to both worms despite their distant relationship, and thus one may assume a similar mesh size for the *Olivella* net. While the two worms generate and regulate the filter current themselves, *Olivella* utilizes the surf current. In its initial phases, however, the current would be too strong for the delicate net, for mechanical reasons. In addition, the sand carried by the turbulent swash and the initially rapid backwash would quickly clog the net. Such a device therefore would be useless for an animal that, unlike *Olivella*, could not sense the current and wait for the right moment to deploy the net. Nevertheless, single grains of sand frequently end up in the *Olivella* net. Here the retraction process ensures that they are not eaten. The wide central part of the propodium creeps with its sharp edge over the inner net surface and automatically strips off all sand grains (Fig. 10c-e).

By burrowing and re-emerging in unison with the incoming waves, *Olivella* can parry the surf, but not the changing tides. As the water falls, fewer and fewer waves reach the strip of beach occupied by *Olivella*. To avoid falling dry completely, the snails burrow out in the maximum current of the next backwash as if on command and allow themselves to be transported a few decimeters seaward in an inverted posture (Fig. 10f). There they burrow in again on a narrow strip so quickly that they can deploy their nets once more in the very next wave that reaches them. When the tide is rising, the change of position proceeds in the same manner, except that burrowing and transporting already occur in the swash current.

In this way, the olivellas are always able to keep to the zone within the surf belt that is most favorable to their feeding habits. In doing so they resemble the crab *Emerita analoga* of the Californian coast, which generally seems to substitute for our snail ecologically in that region. The filtration apparatus and the stimulation processes triggering emergence and tidal migration certainly differ much in detail, but in their basic behavior snail and crab embody the same type of life form.

How little a similarity of life-styles often coincides with a close phylogenetic relationship is demonstrated by the olivids of the genus *Agaronia*, which are closely related to *Olivella*. According to O. SCHUSTER (1956), they occur on the Salvadoran beach in two species (*A. hiatula* and *A. testacea*),⁷⁶ both often next to each other and always in company of *Olivella*, shallowly hidden in the sand like the latter. They even perform their tidal changes of position together with *Olivella*. Otherwise they do not appear on the surface, at least not in the backwash. Consequently, they lack the telltale surface traces, which is why they are found proportionately even less frequently than the much more common *Olivella*, although they considerably exceed it in size. It takes some experience to recognize (from a faint accumulation of magnetite sand) the location of an *Agaronia*.

Olivella columellaris

Figure 10: When acquiring food, the snail body remains hidden in the sand facing landward (a). Only the propodium appears at the surface to spread and retract the mucus net in the backwash (from the left) (b-e). When changing position by swimming (f), the ventral side points upward. The foot serves as a funnel-shaped sail or active swimming organ; other appendages act as stabilizers. When crawling (g) and burrowing, the foot wraps around the shell like a cloak. Slower movements occur by sole crawling, more rapid ones by looping with the propodium.

When digging up *Agaronia*, it will be noticed that they take a different position in the sand than *Olivella*. The latter, like most surf filter feeders, lie with the body axis perpendicular to the coast, and always with the front end pointing landward; for only in this way can they set up their net correctly in the backwash. In *Agaronia*, on the other hand, the head points either to the right or to the left, but always with the body axis parallel to the beach.

This contradiction in the behavior of *Agaronia* is only resolved when one finds a specimen that envelops an *Olivella* with its broad foot and is about to devour it. Like all representatives of the olivids, *Agaronia* is a predator with shark-like radula teeth, and its preference for *Olivella* is also known from Peruvian beaches (OLSSON

1956).⁷⁷ For this reason, *Agaronia* always remains where *Olivella* is present, and also joins its prey species when it changes position on the beach. Otherwise, its behavior must be different, because instead of staying in one place like a net-fisherman, the predatory snail must crawl around searching under the surface of the sand. By always maintaining a beach-parallel course, it automatically stays in the narrow beach-parallel strip where *Olivella* lives.

By the way, *Olivella* may exceptionally crawl in a beach-parallel direction. I observed this once, a few hundred meters inside the mouth of the Estero San Juan del Gozo (Fig. 4). The location is not hit by the full surf, but still was littered with *Olivella* that may have washed up there. They had initially expanded their nets (surface traces!), but had then run dry and now were all crawling — not down to the water, but beach-parallel to the left toward the mouth of the lagoon. This mass migration was short-lived, though. After not more than 60 cm, each snail had made a tight turn and burrowed in the usual direction with respect to the beach.

There would be much more to report on the way *Olivella* crawls across the sand, by no means at a snail's pace but with violent, looper-like movements, how it burrows in seconds, and swims actively up to the water's surface in the aquarium with jellyfish-like movements of the foot. Nor are snails the only inhabitants of the Salvadoran surf sand. A whole series of worms, crustaceans, mollusks, sea urchins, and starfish (cf. SCHUSTER 1956) have adapted, each in its own way, to life in this habitat, offering a host of startling convergences and at the same time original solutions to identical ecological tasks. But this is to be presented in another context. Here the aim was to describe the interconnected life histories of the two snails, focusing only on directly observable forms and processes. How, for example, *Olivella*, which lacks eyes and other conspicuous sense organs, determines the right time to deploy its nets or to change its position, how it finds its correct orientation on the beach, or how such adaptations come about at all, remain even more attractive questions for the future.

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